

Rac-3j

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-110-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08312
Vial:	116	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 110 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 5:44:06 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 6:17:22 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.065	6334056	50.06	407969
2	14.321	6319222	49.94	306956

Asy-3j (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-111-3-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08312
Vial:	118	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 111 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 6:27:50 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 6:46:33 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.064	1008595	3.67	65683
2	14.302	26456111	96.33	1279745

Asy-3j (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-111-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08312
Vial:	117	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 111 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 6:05:59 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 6:41:38 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.068	1148189	3.13	74006
2	14.302	35513291	96.87	1706581